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**APPROACHES TO BUILD OF ADVANCED SECURE SCHEME FOR
DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS**

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Annotation: Standard and special means of database protection and approaches to increase the effectiveness of protection are presented. Algorithms and software tools based on cryptographic, masking and protection models of access control have been developed.

Key words: information security, database control, access control, MAC policy.

Organizations need to use multilevel security approaches to secure DBMS. Multilevel Security (MLS) is a capability that allows information with different classifications to be available in an information system, with users having different security clearances and authorizations, while preventing users from accessing information for which they are not cleared or authorized. Given the extremely high value of the information that could be stored in a military or intelligence database, and the potential damage that could result from the unauthorized disclosure, alteration or loss of such information, preventing users from accessing information for which they are not cleared or authorized requires much more than just implementing an access control policy. In particular, security guards must be put in place to prevent users from gaining access to information for which they are not cleared or authorized through indirect means.

Building a multilevel secure RDBMS has thus posed significant challenges to the database research community. For instance, secure database transaction protocols had to be developed, and a solution to reconcile the conflicting

requirements between data integrity and confidentiality had to be found.

There has been an abundance of research within the last two decades or so in the area of multilevel secure RDBMS. Such re-search has addressed specific aspects of build-ing a multilevel secure RDBMS such as secure transaction protocols, system architectures, or poly instantiation and there is a rich set of publications about those specific aspects. However, the multilevel secure RDBMS research literature surprisingly lacks the kind of publication that would allow someone to get a good understanding about what it takes to build a multilevel secure RDBMS as a whole, as well as to serve as a quick guide for those who might be thinking about building such RDBMS.

Multilevel secure RDBMS architectures can be divided into two general types, depending on whether mandatory access control is enforced by the RDBMS itself or delegated to a trusted operating system. These two general types are the Woods Hole Architecture and the Trusted Subjects Architecture .

Woods Hole Architectures. The Woods Hole architectures are the outcome of a three-week study on trusted data management sponsored by the U.S. Air Force at Woods Hole, Massachusetts, USA in 1982. The subject of this study was the following: Can we build a multilevel secure RDBMS using existing untrusted off-the-shelf RDBMS.

The Woods Hole architectures assume that an untrusted of-the-shelf RDBMS is used to access data and that trusted code is developed around that RDBMS to provide an overall se-ure RDBMS. They can be divided into two main categories: The kernelized architectures and the distributed architectures.

The kernelized architecture uses a trusted operating system and multiple copies of an of-the-shelf RDBMS, where each copy is associated with some trusted front-end. Each pair (trusted front-end, RDBMS) is associated with a particular security level. The trusted operating system enforces its full access control policy on all accesses by the RDBMS to the RDBMS objects. It ensures that data at different security levels is stored separately, and that each copy of the RDBMS gets access to data that is authorized for its associated security level. The latter is possible because the multilevel database is decomposed into multiple single-level databases, where each represents a fragment of the conceptual multilevel database. Each fragment is stored in a single-level operating system object (e.g., a file) which is labeled by the operating system at the corresponding security level, and thus can only be accessed according to the MAC policy of the

operating system.

Figure 1 illustrates a kernelized architecture where one RDBMS is associated with the security level “High” and another RDBMS is associated with the security level “Low”. The RDBMS associated with the security level “High” has access to both the fragment of the database at the high security level and the fragment of the database at the low security level. But the RDBMS associated with the security level “Low” has access only to the fragment of the database at the low security level.

A benefit of this architecture is that data at different security levels is isolated in the database, which allows for higher level assurance. Another benefit is that, assuming an already evaluated operating system, this architecture should minimize the amount of time and effort to evaluate the RDBMS. However, this architecture results in an additional over-head as the trusted operating system needs to separate data at different security levels when it is added to the database and might also need to combine data from different security levels when data is retrieved by an RDBMS copy that is associated with a high security level.

Figure 1. Multilevel secure kernelized RDBMS architecture

The distributed (or replicated) architecture is a variation of the kernelized architecture. It uses multiple copies of the trusted front-end and RDBMS, each associated with its own database storage. In this architecture scheme, an RDBMS at security level 1 contains a replica of every data item that a subject at level 1 can access. Thus, when data is retrieved, the RDBMS retrieves it only from its own database. Another benefit of this architecture is that data is physically separated

into separate hardware databases. However, this scheme results in an additional overhead when data is updated as the various replicas need to be kept in sync.

Trusted Subjects Architectures. The trusted subject architecture is a scheme that contains a trusted RDBMS and a trusted operating system. According to this architecture, the mandatory access control policy is enforced by the RDBMS itself. Database objects (e.g., a table) are stored in operating system objects (e.g., a file) labeled at the highest security level. A database table can contain rows with different security levels. Such rows are distinguished based on their security level which is explicitly stored with each row. This architecture is called “trusted subject” because the RDBMS is privileged to violate the operating system’s MAC policy when accessing database objects. For example, when a user with a low security level queries a database table, the operating system’s object where that table is stored ends up being accessed, which is a violation of the operating system’s MAC policy. But the RDBMS is trusted to return to the users only those rows for which he or she is authorized according to the MAC policy. Figure 2. illustrates a multilevel secure trusted subject RDBMS Architecture.

Figure 2. Multilevel secure trusted subject RDBMS architecture

A benefit of this architecture is that the RDBMS has access to all levels of data at the same time, which minimizes retrieval and up-date processing. However, this architecture results in a special purpose RDBMS that requires a large amount of trusted code to be developed and verified along with the normal RDBMS features.

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